

MaveDB: discovery and interpretation of high-throughput functional assay data

Alan F Rubin

Australian BioCommons

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Types of high-throughput functional assays

MAVE: Multiplexed Assay of Variant Effect

Advances in genomics start with the genes

Variants of Uncertain Significance are a growing problem

High-throughput functional data can help solve VUS

Three key challenges

Data generation

Data sharing and standardization

Translational data models

Data generation

High-throughput functional assays

Library
of genetic
variants

Target

... TAT AAT TCA ATT AGG ATT ...

Variants

... **G**AT AAT TCA ATT AGG ATT ...

... **C**AT TTT TCA ATT AGG ATT ...

... TAT **TTG** TCA ATT AGG ATT ...

... TAT AAT TCA ATT **---** ATT ...

High-throughput functional assays

High-throughput functional assays

Saturation
Genome Editing

High-throughput functional assays

Base Editing

Prime Editing

High-throughput functional assays

High-throughput functional assays

High-throughput functional assays

Heterogeneity is a major challenge for functional data

Yeast

Mammalian Cells

Bacteria

Viruses

Assay System

Fluorescent reporters

Single cell readouts

Assay Readout

Data standardization and sharing

MaveDB

- MaveDB is the database for multiplexed functional data
- Launched in 2019
 - Esposito et al. *Genome Biol.*
- Contains ~800 datasets and 8M variant measurements
- <https://www.mavedb.org>

Millions of variants have been measured by MAVEs

MaveDB data is diverse but mostly human

ACMG genes in MaveDB:

- *BRCA1**
- *KCNQ1*
- *MSH2*
- *PTEN**
- *SCN5A*
- *TP53**
- *CALM1/2/3*

* multiple datasets

Mave Registry tracks data generation efforts

<https://registry.varianteffect.org/>

- Over 100 high-throughput assay projects being tracked
- Hub for community building and collaboration

Hierarchical structure of MaveDB data

Experiment Set contains all assays in a study

Score Set describes the analysis and contains scores/counts

Experiment Set *urn:mavedb:00000013*

Experiment *urn:mavedb:00000013-a*

Score Set *urn:mavedb:00000013-a-1*

Experiment describes one assay and its replicates

MaveDB supports complex experimental designs

Experiment Set *urn:mavedb:00000003*

Experiment *urn:mavedb:00000003-a*

Score Set *urn:mavedb:00000003-a-1*

Score Set *urn:mavedb:00000003-a-2*

Score Set *urn:mavedb:00000003-b-1*

Score Set *urn:mavedb:00000003-b-2*

Experiment *urn:mavedb:00000003-b*

MaveDB supports reanalysis

Experiment Set `urn:mavedb:00000013`

Experiment `urn:mavedb:00000013-a`

Score Set `urn:mavedb:00000013-a-1`

Experiment Set `urn:mavedb:00000101`

Experiment `urn:mavedb:00000101-a`

Score Set `urn:mavedb:00000101-a-1`

Meta-analysis Score Set
depends on one or
more existing score sets

Experiment Set `urn:mavedb:00000102`

Score Set `urn:mavedb:00000102-0-1`

Example of what MaveDB data looks like

hgvs_pro	score	sd	expts	se	lower_ci	upper_ci
p.Gly44Glu	0.849	0.040	4	0.020	0.810	0.889
p.His118Leu	0.382	0.272	10	0.086	0.213	0.550
p.His118Lys	0.313	0.195	5	0.087	0.142	0.484
p.Cys83Asp	1.192	0.444	2	0.314	0.578	1.807
p.Asp252Thr	0.047	0.103	3	0.059	-0.069	0.164
p.Asp52Tyr	0.901	0.118	3	0.068	0.767	1.034

Required

Optional

MaveDB web interface

Automatically-generated
variant effect maps

Curation metadata

Abstract, methods and
other key text elements

The screenshot displays the MaveDB web interface for a PTEN VAMP-seq Combined dataset. The URL is <https://www.mavedb.org/#/score-sets/urn:mavedb:00000102-0-1>. The page title is "PTEN VAMP-seq Combined". Below the title, a description states: "Amino acid scores for variant abundance by massively parallel sequencing (VAMP-seq) applied to PTEN (combination of original and fill-in datasets)." The dataset identifier is "urn:mavedb:00000102-0-1".

The main feature is a variant effect map (VEM) heatmap. The x-axis represents amino acid positions from 1 to 67, and the y-axis represents amino acid types: A, V, L, I, M, F, Y, W, R, H, K, D, E, S, T, N, O, C, P, and a blank row. The heatmap shows a color scale from light blue (low abundance) to dark blue (high abundance), with some yellow and orange spots indicating specific variant effects. A dashed black circle highlights the heatmap area.

Below the heatmap, the curation metadata is displayed:

- Created Aug 25, 2022 Alan Rubin
- Last updated Aug 25, 2022 Alan Rubin
- Published Aug 25, 2022
- License: CCo (Public domain)
- Member of urn:mavedb:00000102-0
- Current version urn:mavedb:00000102-0-1
- Meta-analyzes PTEN VAMP-seq · PTEN VAMP-seq Fill-in
- Download files [Scores](#) [Mapped Variants](#)

Below the metadata is the "Abstract" section, which begins with the text: "This experiment used massively parallel sequencing (VAMP-seq) to measure the abundance scores of new variants in the PTEN gene, as well as to validate abundance measurements for previously studied variants in the PTEN gene. The resulting PTEN abundance dataset demonstrates the ability of large-scale variant functional data paired with cancer genomics datasets and follow-up assays to understand how uncharacterized cancer-associated variants contribute to oncogenesis."

MaveDB API

- Supports data upload and download via API
- Bulk download and versioned data releases later this year
- MaveTools Python SDK in development

The screenshot displays the Swagger UI for the MaveDB API. The endpoint is `GET /api/v1/score-sets/{urn}` with the description "Show Score Set". The parameters section shows a required string parameter `urn` with the value `urn:mavedb:00000102-0-1`. The "Execute" button is highlighted in blue. Below the parameters, the "Responses" section shows a `200` status code with a detailed JSON response body and response headers.

Parameters

Name	Description
<code>urn</code> * required string (path)	urn:mavedb:00000102-0-1

Responses

Code 200

Response body

```
{
  "title": "PTEN VAMP-seq Combined",
  "methodText": "Abundance scores from the original and fill-in datasets were aggregated and a composite score was calculated by taking the mean of all 15 replicate scores (8 from the original, 7 for the fill-in).",
  "abstractText": "This experiment used massively parallel sequencing (VAMP-seq) to measure the abundance scores of new variants in the PTEN gene, as well as to validate abundance measurements for previously studied variants in the PTEN gene. The resulting PTEN abundance dataset demonstrates the ability of large-scale variant functional data paired with cancer genomics datasets and follow-up assays to understand how uncharacterized cancer-associated variants contribute to oncogenesis.",
  "shortDescription": "Amino acid scores for variant abundance by massively parallel sequencing (VAMP-seq) applied to PTEN (combination of original and fill-in datasets).",
  "extraMetadata": {},
  "urn": "urn:mavedb:00000102-0-1",
  "numVariants": 5477,
  "experiment": {
    "title": "Meta-analysis of urn:mavedb:00000101-a-1, urn:mavedb:00000101-a-1",
    "shortDescription": "Meta-analysis of urn:mavedb:00000101-a-1, urn:mavedb:00000101-a-1",
    "extraMetadata": {},
    "urn": "urn:mavedb:00000102-0",
    "createdBy": {
      "orcidId": "0000-0003-1474-605X",
      "firstName": "Alan",
      "lastName": "Rubin"
    },
    "modifiedBy": {
      "orcidId": "0000-0003-1474-605X",
      "firstName": "Alan",
      "lastName": "Rubin"
    },
    "creationDate": "2022-08-25",
    "modificationDate": "2022-08-25"
  }
}
```

Response headers

```
content-length: 7037
content-type: application/json
date: Sun, 24 Mar 2024 10:38:42 GMT
server: uvicorn
x-firefox-spydy: h2
```

Minimum information standards and a controlled vocabulary

Minimum information standards and a controlled vocabulary

Using standards to promote data deposition

Mapping MaveDB variants to the human genome

Mapping MaveDB variants to the human genome

HGVS is a common format for human variants

HGVS can become very complex and hard to parse

```
NC_000019.10:g.44908822C>T
```

```
NC_000008.11:g.(131500001_136400000)  
ins[(127300001_131500000)  
(131500001_136400000)inv]
```

GA4GH VRS is verbose but easily computable

```
{  
  "id": "ga4gh:VA._YNe5V9kyxdfkGU0NRyCMHDSKHL4YNvc",  
  "location": {  
    "interval": {  
      "end": {  
        "type": "Number",  
        "value": 44908822  
      },  
      "start": {  
        "type": "Number",  
        "value": 44908821  
      },  
      "type": "SequenceInterval"  
    },  
    "sequence_id": "refseq:NC_000019.10",  
    "type": "SequenceLocation"  
  },  
  "state": {  
    "sequence": "T",  
    "type": "LiteralSequenceExpression"  
  },  
  "type": "Allele"  
}
```

NC_000019.10:g.44908822C>T

Standards and mapping enable sharing and integration

Building clinical data models

Brief introduction to the ACMG evidence framework

gnomAD is here

in silico predictors are here

MAVEs are here

	Benign		Pathogenic			
	Strong	Supporting	Supporting	Moderate	Strong	Very Strong
Population Data	MAF is too high for disorder <i>BA1/BS1</i> OR observation in controls inconsistent with disease penetrance <i>BS2</i>			Absent in population databases <i>PM2</i>	Prevalence in affecteds statistically increased over controls <i>PS4</i>	
Computational And Predictive Data		Multiple lines of computational evidence suggest no impact on gene /gene product <i>BP4</i> Missense in gene where only truncating cause	Multiple lines of computational evidence support a deleterious effect on the gene /gene product <i>PP3</i>	Novel missense change at an amino acid residue where a different pathogenic missense change has been seen before <i>PM5</i>	Same amino acid change as an established pathogenic variant <i>PS1</i>	Predicted null variant in a gene where LOF is a known mechanism of disease <i>PS1</i>
Functional Data	Well-established functional studies show no deleterious effect <i>BS3</i>		Missense in gene with low rate of benign missense variants and path. missenses common <i>PP2</i>	Pr	Well-established functional studies show a deleterious effect <i>PS3</i>	
			Co-segregation with disease in multiple affected family members <i>PP1</i>	or fu wi va		
De novo Data				<i>De novo</i> (without paternity & maternity confirmed) <i>PM6</i>	<i>De novo</i> (paternity & maternity confirmed) <i>PS2</i>	
Allelic Data		Observed in <i>trans</i> with a dominant variant <i>BP2</i> Observed in <i>cis</i> with a pathogenic variant <i>BP2</i>		For recessive disorders, detected in <i>trans</i> with a pathogenic variant <i>PM3</i>		
Other Database		Reputable source w/out shared data = benign <i>BP6</i>	Reputable source = pathogenic <i>PP5</i>			
Other Data		Found in case with an alternate cause <i>BP5</i>	Patient's phenotype or FH highly specific for gene <i>PP4</i>			

Using MAVE variants clinically

Evaluating the strength of a MAVE assay

Many VUS can be reclassified using MAVE data

BRCA1 classifications with MAVE data

TP53 classifications with MAVE data

PTEN classifications with MAVE data

Presenting MAVE data for clinical variant classification

MAVE-oriented visualizations to help interpret scores

Clinical evidence codes and odds path where available

Links to other data sources

Developing a new global standard for functional data

Global Alliance
for Genomics & Health
Collaborate. Innovate. Accelerate.

Enabling discoverability and translation

The ClinVar logo, which includes the text "ClinVar" in large white letters and "Clinically relevant variation" in smaller white letters below it, set against a dark blue background. To the right of the logo is a DNA sequence: CTGATGGTATGGGGCCAAGAGATAT, AGGTACGGCTGTCATCACTTAGAC, AGGGCTGGGATAAAAAGTCAGGGCA, CATGGTGCATCTGACTCCTGAGGA, CAGGTTGGTATCAAGGTTACAAGAC, GCACTGACTCTCTCTGCCTATTGGT.

Health
Pathology

Educating clinicians about MAVEs

**wellcome
connecting
science**

engagement | learning | research | training

Clinical Application of
MAVE Data workshop

Allen et al. (2024) Eur J Hum Genet.

... making sense of your genes

Needs assessments and workshops for clinicians and researchers

High-throughput functional data can help solve VUS

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Estelle Da
Nick Moore
Ashley Snyder
Jeremy Stone
Ben Capodanno
Sally Grindstaff

University of Washington

Lara Muffley
Doug Fowler
Lea Starita
Andrew Stergachis
Abbye McEwen
Brian Shirts
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AVE is organizing the international community

Atlas of Variant Effects

<https://www.varianteffect.org/>

